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The State of Music Education in English Schools: A Landscape Briefing Paper

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Background

Official DfE Data shows that music education in state schools continues to be under pressure. As with all statistics, this can be a complex picture and the reasons for the figures are not always clear. Despite this lack of certainty, some statistical differentials are stark, indicating there are issues to be investigated to safeguard young people’s entitlement to music education in schools.

Music Teacher Recruitment

According to DfE figures ¹ the picture for recruitment of music teachers is as follows:

Year	DfE Secondary Music Teacher Target	Total Secondary Music Teacher Actual
2019 – 2020	392	312
2020 – 2021	385	469
2021 – 2022	540	386
2022 – 2023	470	292
2023 – 2024	790	216
2024 – 2025	820	331
2025 – 2026	565	Not yet known

Commentary: The DfE recruitment target for music teachers has been consistently rising until the current year, from 392 in 2019/20 to 820 in 2024/25. Recruitment to secondary music training courses has been consistently below this figure with the exception of 2020/21, and this spike was potentially linked to Covid. It remains to be seen what music teacher training retention will be like this academic year, although last year’s target was missed by 60%.

¹ **Sources:** Column 1: [table_1_subject_characteristics initial-teacher-training-census-2024-25](#). Available at: [Initial Teacher Training Census, Academic year 2024/25 - Explore education statistics - GOV.UK](#) Column 2: [table_2_subjects_target_time_series](#) Available at: [Table 2 - ITT new entrants and targets by subject time series, Data set from Initial Teacher Training Census - Explore education statistics - GOV.UK](#)

Music Teacher Workforce

According to DfE data²:

Year	Total Number of Secondary Music Teachers	Music Teachers Teaching Key Stage 3 (11-14-year-olds)	Music Teachers Teaching Key Stage 4 (Level 2)	Music Teachers Teaching Key Stage 5 (Level 3)
2011 – 2012	8043	7380	5405	3191
2012 – 2013	7432	6894	5362	3182
2013 – 2014	7268	6764	5330	3176
2014 – 2015	7109	6620	5187	3075
2015 – 2016	6862	6410	5051	2858
2016 – 2017	6720	6328	4913	2650
2017 – 2018	6480	6174	4659	2358
2018 – 2019	6525	6237	4623	2245
2019 – 2020	6543	6179	4649	2169
2020 – 2021	6837	6439	4708	2099
2021 – 2022	7003	6649	4861	2198
2022 – 2023	7184	6807	4858	2156
2023 – 2024	7449	7060	4882	2105
2024 – 2025	7610	7209	4975	2060

Commentary: Since 2011, the total number of secondary music teachers has fallen by 433. The lowest number of total music teachers was in 2017/2018, when it was 6,480. Numbers declined steadily between 2011 and 2018 and have increased between 2018/19 and 2025.

Key Stage 3 music teachers have decreased by 171 between 2011/12 and 2024/25. They were at their highest in 2011/12 at 7380 and their lowest in 2017/18 at 6174.

Key Stage 4 (level 2) music teachers have decreased by 430 between 2011/12 and 2024/25. They were at their highest in 2011/12 at 5,405 and their lowest in 2018/19 at 4,623.

² **Source:** workforce_secondary-subjects_taught_2011_2024 spreadsheet. Available at: <https://explore-education-statistics.service.gov.uk/find-statistics/school-workforce-in-england/2024>

Key Stage 5 (level 3) music teachers have decreased by 1,131 between 2011/12 and 2024/25. They were at their highest in 2011/12 at 3,191 and their lowest in 2024/25 at 2,060.

Please note that there were 7,449 music teachers during 2023/2024 and there are 7,610 in 2024/2025.

Impact of workforce reduction:

Although the overall workforce decline is 5%, the details of the impacts at different school ages is telling and the potential impacts are concerning. Key Stage 5 music (A-level or equivalent) music has experienced a stark and concerning workforce decline of 35% in 13 years. This loss of expertise may prove very difficult to recover, as not all music teachers are able to immediately teach at this level, especially during their first year following qualifying. The workforce for Key Stage 4 has fallen by 8%, which is also concerning and it will also take time to replenish the stock of available music teachers with the necessary experience and expertise to teach at this level. This will in turn impact on the Key Stage 5 (Level 3) pipeline. Key Stage 3 music teachers have declined by 2% over the same period, so has remained broadly stable.

Music Teacher Teaching Time

DfE data ³ gives a picture of teaching time:

Year	Total Music Teaching Hours	Music Teaching Hours Key Stage 3 (11-14-year-olds)	Music Teaching Hours Key Stage 4 (Level 2)	Music Teaching Hours Key Stage 5 (Level 3)
2011 – 2012	93095	59740	19389	13965
2012 – 2013	91661	58076	19509	14077
2013 – 2014	90893	57173	19685	14035
2014 – 2015	88643	55969	19158	13516
2015 – 2016	85505	54877	18271	12356
2016 – 2017	83543	54625	17767	11152
2017 – 2018	80143	53184	17108	9851
2018 – 2019	79305	53065	17010	9230
2019 – 2020	79633	53281	17391	8961
2020 – 2021	83663	56140	18438	9084
2021 – 2022	86480	58928	18114	9439
2022 – 2023	85639	59273	17430	8936
2023 – 2024	86628	60515	17566	8548
2024 – 2025	87461	61564	17556	8341

Commentary: Since 2011, the total number of teaching hours for music in schools has fallen by 5,634. This reduction has been a steady year-on-year decline and raises concerns for the erosion of the status and access young people have to music in schools.

Teaching hours at Key Stage 3 declined between 2011/12 and 2019/19, with an increase to a more stable footing from 2023 onwards where they have exceeded their 2011 numbers.

However, what is most concerning is the decline in hours in examination school years. Between 2011/12 and 2024/25, school hours for Key Stage 4 (Level 2) declined by 1,833, a decrease of 9%. As the number of hours for Key Stage 4 has been identical for the previous

³ **Source:** workforce_secondary-subjects_taught_2011_2024 spreadsheet. Available at: <https://explore-education-statistics.service.gov.uk/find-statistics/school-workforce-in-england/2024>

two academic years, it looks as though this may be a continuing situation. The current hours are only 546 hours higher than the lowest level in 2018/19 and despite the temporary upward lift in 2020/21 and 2021/22, potentially due to school's management of the Covid-19 pandemic, such low levels appear set to continue. Hours for music teaching at Key Stage 4 (Level 2) have been in the region of 17,000 for 7 out of the past 12 years and analysis needs to reach as far back as 2014/15 before figures of 19,000 hours or more can be found.

Taught hours for Key Stage 5 (level 3) are catastrophic, with a decrease of 5,624 hours, a fall of 40%. This reduction in hours may indicate qualifications such as A-level music being restricted and not offered in school Key Stage 5 options for young people. It may also indicate that where such qualifications are offered, they are not given the same proportion of time that they were during 2011/12, baring in potential disadvantage for those wishing to pursue a musical pathway to higher levels of achievement.

Qualification numbers

According to Ofqual⁴, The Profile for GCSE Music entries is as follows:

Year	Number of candidates
2008	54230
2009	48350
2010	46045
2011	43125
2012	41510
2013	41580
2014	42670
2015	43665
2016	41865
2017	38375
2018	35530
2019	34740
2020	43685
2021	35200
2022	33795
2023	29730
2024	32285

The number of entries for GCSE Music has therefore fallen by 40% over 16 years. If last year's numbers were an anomaly, the figure is even starker, with a fall of 45% between 2008 and 2023.

⁴ **Source:** GCSE Outcomes in England, Ofqual. Available from: [GCSE outcomes in England](#)

The profile for A-level music entries in Ofqual data ⁵is as follows:

Year	Number of candidates
2008	9465
2009	9220
2010	8790
2011	8905
2012	8370
2013	7795
2014	7355
2015	6820
2016	6295
2017	5610
2018	5440
2019	5125
2020	5030
2021	5040
2022	5270
2023	4930
2024	4985

This means that there has been a fall of 48% in the number of A-level entries since 2010, a figure of great concern.

⁵ Source: A-level outcomes in England, Ofqual. Available at: [A level outcomes in England](#)

Music education in state schools and independent sector

Comparisons between these sectors are difficult due to the patchiness of data and it is problematic to compare young people’s access to music and what this might mean in these differing settings, not least due to varying school characteristics.

However, we can say that in 2024, only 45% of state schools working at Level 3 entered a music student for an exam. By comparison, in the independent sector, 59% of schools entered a student for a music qualification.

In 2020, there were 1,615 state schools (non-independent schools) that entered at least one student for a Level 3 Music qualification (this includes vocational qualifications as well as A-level). By 2024, there were only 986 state schools doing this, which is a drop of around 39%. During the same time period, the independent sector saw a drop from 417 to 330 schools entering music students, a 21% drop. This is a significant difference, although it is difficult to know precisely what the causes or the factors involved with this might be.

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⁶ Source: Compare School Performance (DfE): <https://www.compare-school-performance.service.gov.uk/>. Chart drawn from an unpublished analysis by Stephen Tatlow (shared with permission).

Further lines of enquiry

Our research addresses some of the outcomes of declining numbers and inequalities presented throughout this paper. We are concerned that ‘Covid-safe’ measures as designed and implemented by schools may have fundamentally altered educational practices and that this is impacting young people’s access to equitable music education in schools. We have written about this in our **‘teaching music unmusically’ article**:

<https://doi.org/10.1002/curj.236>

Our concerns about access to qualification levels in music are long held. Music cannot be taken by young people where it is not offered. We have more extensive analysis of the impacts of **A-level in our discussion paper** from a few years ago here:

<https://bcuassets.blob.core.windows.net/docs/a-level-report-290621-pdf-132695100641559063.pdf>.